

HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE LIVER DURING THYROTOXICOSIS

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Abstract: The aim of the study was to examine the morphological changes in the liver during experimental thyrotoxicosis. The experiments were conducted on 36 white outbred rats, which were divided into control and experimental groups. It was found that during experimental thyrotoxicosis, dystrophic, atrophic, and destructive changes develop in hepatocytes of laboratory white rats. These changes are most pronounced on the 60th day of the experiment. By the end of the experiment, these phenomena worsened even further.

Keywords: Thyrotoxicosis, liver vessels, hepatocytes

Introduction. Thyroid diseases rank first among endocrine pathologies in terms of prevalence. Thyrotoxicosis is one of the most common endocrine disorders. The prevalence of thyrotoxicosis in women ranges from 4% to 21%, and in men from 3% to 16% [6,11]. Subclinical thyrotoxicosis occurs 2 to 2.5 times more often in women than in men. In older age groups, the prevalence of subclinical thyrotoxicosis is higher, reaching 10–16%. Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in regulating basal metabolism. A decrease in their concentration sharply reduces metabolic levels, leading to increased fat deposits, which can trigger the development of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD). Liver diseases are associated with impaired secretion and metabolism of thyroid hormones [1,5]. Liver pathologies result in dysfunction or disruption of hormonal interactions [2,3,7]. Thyroid hormones, thyroxine (T4), and triiodothyronine (T3) are synthesized and secreted by follicular epithelial cells of the thyroid gland and contain an iodine molecule. These hormones regulate all types of metabolism in the body, affecting all cells and stimulating tissue respiration. Therefore, even a slight deficiency of thyroid hormones leads to severe disorders [10,14]. Thyroid hormones increase overall metabolism, oxygen consumption, and heat production in tissues, primarily affecting the heart, liver, and kidneys. According to various authors, thyrotoxicosis can cause fatty liver dystrophy, cirrhosis, and hepatic coma [4,9].

Research Objectives. The study aimed to determine the nature of morphological changes in the liver during experimental thyrotoxicosis.

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted on female Wistar rats weighing 250–300 g. All rats reached sexual maturity at 8–9 months. Healthy rats were selected for the experiments and were kept under optimal conditions. The experiments followed international recommendations from the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals.

Thyroid hormone levels were measured using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) with diagnostic kits for T3, T4, and TSH (DRG International Inc., Germany): total triiodothyronine (T3), total thyroxine (T4), and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). The white laboratory rats were divided into three groups:

- **Group 1:** 24 female laboratory rats were administered L-thyroxine daily at a dose of 2 mcg per kg of body weight to induce experimental thyrotoxicosis.
- **Group 2:** 24 female laboratory rats received the same dose of L-thyroxine to induce experimental thyrotoxicosis.
- **Group 3:** 24 female laboratory rats were administered L-thyroxine (2 mcg per kg) and the antioxidant Mexidol (0.3 mg per kg) daily.

Results and Discussion. The study showed that the rat liver is located behind the diaphragm and constitutes 48% of the total body mass. The liver consists of six lobes: right and left lateral lobes, right and left central lobes, caudate, and accessory lobes. The inner surface of each lobe has indentations (gates) through which blood vessels enter and hepatic ducts exit. In the early stages of the experiment (3, 7, and 21 days), macroscopic examination showed no visible changes in the rat liver. Its weight and size corresponded to control group parameters. No microscopic changes were detected, and the histological structure was preserved. During experimental thyrotoxicosis, liver mass gradually increased (by 10% on day 30 compared to the control group) and by 45% at the end of the experiment (day 90). The most significant increase was observed on day 60 (35%). After 30 days, minor vascular disturbances, such as moderate venous congestion and stasis, were noted. In perivascular spaces, focal edema was detected, with swelling and homogenization of collagen fibers in some areas (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Large focal lymphocytic infiltration in the liver stroma (30 days). Staining: Hematoxylin and eosin, x400.

On day 60, vascular disturbances persisted as mild venous congestion. Edema was found predominantly around the central vein in the liver stroma. Some hepatocytes in the central lobule contained small vacuoles. Fibrinoid swelling of small arterial walls was noted. Hepatocytes were swollen, with vacuolated cytoplasm. Hydropic dystrophy was focal. Vascular disturbances, such as venous congestion and stasis, persisted but were more pronounced than in earlier stages. After 90 days, diffuse perisinusoidal edema, edema of portal tracts, and swelling around central veins were observed. The liver stroma showed swelling and degradation of connective tissue, accumulation of glycosaminoglycans, and disintegration of collagen fibers. Small focal infiltrates of lymphocytes, histiocytes, and occasional plasma cells were detected for the first time. At this stage, all hepatocytes exhibited hydropic dystrophy. In addition to hydropic dystrophy, ballooning degeneration foci were observed. Fibroblast proliferation around blood vessels was evident. Dystrophic changes were diffuse, most pronounced in the central lobule. Increased fibroblast proliferation around blood vessels was noted (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Diffuse perisinusoidal edema in rat liver (60 days). Staining: Hematoxylin and eosin, x400.

Conclusion. Thus, during experimental thyrotoxicosis, dystrophic, atrophic, and destructive changes develop in hepatocytes, along with diffuse interstitial edema, lymphocytic infiltration, and stromal fibrosis. These changes were most pronounced on the 60th day of the experiment.

References

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